

Guidelines for the annotation of *Nephrops norvegicus* UWTV videos

Oscar Papini¹, Enrico Cecapolli², Filippo Domenichetti², Michela Martinelli²,
Gabriele Pieri¹, Marco Reggiannini¹, Lorenzo Zacchetti^{2,3}

¹Institute of Information Science and Technologies (ISTI),
National Research Council of Italy, Via G. Moruzzi 1, 56124 Pisa, Italy

²Institute for Marine Biological Resources and Biotechnology (IRBIM),
National Research Council of Italy, Largo Fiera della Pesca 2, 60125 Ancona, Italy

³Department of Biological, Geological, and Environmental Sciences (BiGeA),
Alma Mater Studiorum – University of Bologna, Piazza di Porta S. Donato 1, 40126 Bologna, Italy

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Introduction

Given a UWTV footage sequence, an annotator can identify two possible objects’ categories related to *Nephrops norvegicus*: the **entrance** (individual aperture located on the sandy surface of the seafloor) and the **burrow** (a system of entrances connected by underground tunnels). According to the currently adopted protocol, the number of burrows in a UWTV survey is estimated in real time, by visually inspecting the video while playing back. With this approach, the annotator is primarily concerned with directly counting the overall number of burrows recognized in the video. Eventually, the resulting aggregate number will be exploited to provide a rough estimate of the *Nephrops norvegicus*’ density in the surveyed area.

This document describes a methodology conceived to create ground truth datasets that may be exploited in the implementation of object detection and classification algorithms, tailored on the *Nephrops norvegicus*. In fact, supervised machine learning algorithms usually require considerable amounts of annotated data to carry out the training stage. The greater the size of the annotated dataset, the stronger the required effort from the annotators. This methodology aims at accurately annotating a sequence of frames extracted at equally spaced time steps (usually lower than a second). At every step, the annotator manually marks each instance, observed in its corresponding frame, through a rectangular bounding box that is interactively placed thanks to a dedicated interface (see Section 2). Entrances and burrows will be annotated with separate labels (“Entrance” and “Burrow” respectively, with an additional label “AmbiguousEntrance” for ambiguous entrances—see below) and each annotation will include the observation time (with respect to the video time range) and minimum delimiting area (with respect to the video frame coordinate system). The result of the proposed frame-by-frame approach must be returned as a list of annotations, with each record reporting the object label, the spatial coordinates of the bounding box and the time of annotation (see below for examples).

Annotating UWTV data according to the frame-by-frame approach may put the marine biologists under heavy strain. For example, the annotation of 1 minute lasting video, at 25 frames per second (fps), requires the accurate visual inspection of each and every one of the resulting 1500 frames. For the purposes of this work, a dedicated tool is proposed¹, exploiting the simple fact that objects in a video usually appear in many consecutive frames with similar features. Through a similarity-based recognition, the tag associated with an

¹ <https://shorturl.at/pd3GF>

annotated object can be extended to every frame where that object is visible. This allows to effectively reduce the manual effort, since the tool will take as input a set of annotations obtained at a rate below the video native one (usually 2–3 fps, thus generating 120–180 annotated frames per minute) and will automatically extend the number of annotations. The actual boosting number depends on various factors, primarily on the video frame rate and on the time of persistence of objects in the video, in turn related to the sledge speed.

It is worth pointing out once more that the key motivation behind the publication of these guidelines is to provide the correct input for machine learning algorithms and for the mentioned boosting procedure: to this aim the frames extracted from the UWTV footage must be annotated following all the precautions detailed hereafter. The following Section 1 contains a list of the most important rules to be followed to achieve a proper annotation; Section 2 concerns a description of the most interesting and publicly available annotation tools.

1. Rules for a correct annotation

Ideally the proposed annotation technique should replicate as accurately as possible the mental process that guides the biologist throughout the classical approach to the counting task. Thus, the bounding box delimiting the area occupied by an object of interest should include every visual feature that an annotator takes into consideration to label that object.

Some important aspects affecting the annotation process are further discussed in the following.

Annotation area

For each recorded video, it is necessary to limit the area of the frames where the bounding boxes can be drawn. However, a unique definition of this area, suitable for any video, cannot be provided since it depends on the specific characteristics of the video itself. In particular, the annotators and ISTI-CNR should preemptively agree on the definition of the annotation area.

As an example, in the picture below it is shown the annotation area relative to UW videos recorded in the Pomo/Jabuka Pit area in the Adriatic Sea (inside the yellow trapezoid): parts from the left, right and bottom of the frame have been cut because of the presence of artefacts due to the analog-to-digital conversion, and also because of the abundance of dust raised by the sledge; the upper part is excluded because – besides the presence of the overlaid date and time – the perspective distortion, especially at the low resolution of the videos, translates into less usable data.

Each relevant object contained in the annotation area should be tagged with a bounding box: in case an entrance is acknowledged only in the lower part of the video but was already visible **and contained in the annotation area** in a previous frame, the annotators should go back to that frame and add the corresponding bounding box.

Entrance annotation

An “Entrance” bounding box should identify only the whole entrance and every related visual feature (e.g. the sediment ejecta if present).

If possible, bounding boxes relating to different apertures should not intersect.

Videos undergoing a preliminary analog-to-digital conversion process may be affected by systematic disturbances. Image signals at the boundary regions (picture sides) can be distorted during the conversion, so care must be taken in placing the object bounding box, possibly avoiding the inclusion of such spurious factors. These signal's artefacts feature intensity values that may be seriously anomalous compared to the surrounding pixels. This may represent an issue for the boosting procedure mentioned in the Introduction, since that tool basically looks for similar patterns in the frame sequence. Therefore, these anomalies must be carefully excluded from the annotation bounding box to avoid failures of the boosting algorithm. The following list includes some of the issues to be avoided.

- As a general rule the bounding box must not include any systematic equipment-related artefact, such as:
 - a. the mentioned signal anomalies, typically located at the frame boundaries (left figure below);
 - b. equipment components appearing in the field of view, such as the sledge skates or visual markers physically delimiting the counting area, e.g. wires or laser stripes (right figure below).

- The inclusion, even partial, in the bounding box of any environmental anomaly not strictly related to the aperture to be tagged must be avoided. Examples of such disturbances are:
 - a. sand clouds;
 - b. shadows;
 - c. rocks;
 - d. fauna.

Ambiguous entrance annotation

An “Entrance” bounding box should be used to label only those openings in the seabed that can be attributed to the *N. norvegicus* species with high confidence. If this attribution is uncertain but plausible due to contextual aspects, e.g. an entrance with no clear geometrical features but likely to be part of a burrow due to proximity with other *N. norvegicus* entrances, a label “AmbiguousEntrance” can be used.

Despite this, **the “AmbiguousEntrance” label must be used as little as possible**, since an effective training of a *N. norvegicus* Entrance detector is based on unambiguous annotations of “Entrance” targets, that should therefore represent the largest part of the annotated dataset. In any case, a relevant aspect to consider when in doubt about this annotation, is that every opening that is neither labelled “Entrance” nor “AmbiguousEntrance” will be surely regarded as non-*Nephrops*.

The practical rules for the annotation of an ambiguous entrance are the same as the ones for the certain entrances, explained above.

In the following, “AmbiguousEntrance” boxes will be drawn in yellow-golden color (as opposed to the green “Entrance” boxes).

Burrow annotation

A system of entrances corresponding to a burrow is tagged with the corresponding “Burrow” label. The corresponding bounding box must be placed in order to include each and every bounding box corresponding to the entrances.

More in detail:

- The bounding box of a “Burrow” must completely include every bounding box of its entrances.

- An “Entrance” bounding box can be completely included in at most one “Burrow” bounding box only.

- The bounding box of a “Burrow” may include the forbidden artefacts described in the previous “Entrance annotation” section (e.g. the laser in the right figure).

- A “Burrow” bounding box should always include at least two “Entrance” boxes; any isolated opening (e.g. because the other openings of the burrow are not visible in the frame) will be considered as part of a burrow by default, so it is not necessary to draw a further “Burrow” box around it.

- A “Burrow” box should not include non-tagged entrances (e.g. because they cannot certainly be identified as belonging to a *Nephrops norvegicus* burrow). In this case you can either leave out the non-tagged opening (if it is considered non-*Nephrops*) or use an “AmbiguousEntrance” label.

- Annotations of the same objects appearing in different frames must be coherent, i.e. either they are all labeled (with the same tag) or no one is. For example, in the following images the frame (b) comes 0.5 seconds after frame (a), but the two “Entrance” boxes in (a) do not appear again in (b), despite being in some way recognised by the dimension and position of the “Burrow” box, and a new “Entrance” box is added to the system. A correct annotation of frames (a) and (b) is depicted in panels (c) and (d).

- As a partial exception to the previous rule, bounding boxes related to the same entrance appearing in different frames can vary their labels between “AmbiguousEntrance” and “Entrance”. In other words, an entrance identified with an “AmbiguousEntrance” box in a frame may have an “Entrance” box instead in the following frame, or vice versa. In the example below, the right-most opening on the system changes its label from “AmbiguousEntrance” to “Entrance”.

- In case the same burrow has a variable number of openings in different images (e.g. because some of them are not yet/no longer visible in the frame), you can just draw the “Burrow” box around all the visible entrances. In this case it does not matter that the burrow has a different number of entrances in different frames—it is however important that, if two or more entrances belong to a burrow in a frame and are still visible in a subsequent frame, then they still belong to the same burrow also in that frame.

2. Annotation Tools

As mentioned, the result of a frame-by-frame approach will be a list of records, e.g. a csv file, with each record containing annotated information about the observed instance of an object. Since several tools can serve this purpose, a survey concerning the several available solutions has been conducted.² Eventually, two publicly available softwares have been identified as the best ones fitting our purposes. They are described in the following.

CVAT

CVAT (Computer Vision Annotation Tool; <https://www.cvat.ai>) is an open source images and videos annotation platform initially developed by a research group at Intel before becoming independent. The source code is available on GitHub (<https://github.com/cvat-ai/cvat>). The company offers an online version of the tool, hosted on their servers, requiring the setup of an account, either free (albeit with some limitations) or paid (without said limitations, and with additional support and features). The main downside of the free account is that the number of projects and tasks is limited to 3 projects and 10 tasks total (and max. 5 tasks per project). In any case, as with any other online service, the use of CVAT online requires uploading data to a remote server—clearly, only the uploader and their collaborators have access to them, but this is an aspect to be taken into consideration nonetheless.

Installation

This section describes briefly how to install a local copy of CVAT within a Windows environment. Further information, including the installation instructions for other OSes (Mac OS, Ubuntu Linux), can be found at <https://docs.cvat.ai/docs/administration/basics/installation/>.

CVAT installation is not as straightforward as a double-click on an exe file, but is not a complex procedure overall. CVAT runs as a Docker container, which means that the Docker containers manager has to be installed preemptively. This in turn requires WSL (Windows Subsystem for Linux), a feature that allows Windows users to run a Linux environment natively. Moreover, CVAT is distributed via GitHub, so Git is required to retrieve the source code.

² O. Papini. *A Comparison Between Image Annotation Software for Computer Vision*. Zenodo, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13899145>

1. Install WSL

Detailed instructions on how to install WSL can be found at <https://learn.microsoft.com/windows/wsl/install>. The procedure with standard options is quite simple: one just opens a terminal window with administrative privileges by right-clicking either **Windows PowerShell** and choosing “Run as administrator”.

Then, type “wsl --install” and press Enter. This will activate WSL functions and install an Ubuntu distribution of Linux on the PC. Afterwards, reboot the system.

```
Amministratore: Prompt dei c
Microsoft Windows [Versione 10.0.22631.4112]
(c) Microsoft Corporation. Tutti i diritti riservati.

C:\Users\oscar>wsl --install
```

After the reboot, you will be prompted to create a (local) UNIX user account, so choose a username and a password. (Note that when you type the password, no character will be shown—this is a default behaviour for Linux systems! Don't worry, the password is still being typed in.)

```
oscar@qinglong: ~
Ubuntu è già installato.
Avvio di Ubuntu in corso...
Installing, this may take a few minutes...
Please create a default UNIX user account. The username does not need to match your Windows username.
For more information visit: https://aka.ms/wslusers
Enter new UNIX username: oscar
New password:
Retype new password:
passwd: password updated successfully
Installation successful!
To run a command as administrator (user "root"), use "sudo <command>".
See "man sudo_root" for details.

Welcome to Ubuntu 22.04.3 LTS (GNU/Linux 5.15.153.1-microsoft-standard-WSL2 x86_64)

 * Documentation:  https://help.ubuntu.com
 * Management:    https://landscape.canonical.com
 * Support:       https://ubuntu.com/advantage

This message is shown once a day. To disable it please create the
/home/oscar/.hushlogin file.
oscar@qinglong:~$
```

Now WSL is installed. The default prompt is “<username>@<pc-name>:~\$”, you can type “exit” and press Enter to close the Terminal window.

2. Install Docker

Again, we refer to the page <https://docs.docker.com/desktop/install/windows-install/> for the complete installation instructions. First of all, download from <https://www.docker.com> the Docker Desktop Installer (beware, the file is quite heavy).

Then execute “Docker Desktop Installer.exe” by double-clicking on it. After the installation, you will be prompted to reboot the system. After reboot, you will be asked to accept the Docker Subscription Service Agreement and to provide an email address (or create an account). **Do not provide it, nor create a new account.** Only “anonymous” Docker is able to retrieve the containers of CVAT in step 4 below—if you are logged in with your account, you will get a “401 Unauthorized” error.

For use with CVAT, you should enable the integration of Docker with the Linux distribution that we installed. To do so, inside Docker Desktop, click on “Settings” (1), “Resources” (2), “WSL integration” (3), activate the switch (4) and finally click on “Apply & restart” (5).

3. Install Git

Git (<https://git-scm.com>) is a popular version control system that is used to manage the files of any project. To install it for Windows, download the latest standalone installer from the site and execute it.

The installation wizard will guide you through the installation. You can leave any option as it is by default.

4. Install CVAT

It is finally time to install CVAT. The first step is to retrieve the source code using Git. From the Start Menu in Windows, open the Linux distribution installed with WSL (in our case **Ubuntu**). A Terminal window will appear; inside it, type

```
git clone https://github.com/cvat-ai/cvat
```

and press Enter. Wait for the system to download all the source files of CVAT, then move to the newly created "cvat" folder with

```
cd cvat
```

and create the Docker containers with

```
docker compose up -d
```

```
oscar@qinglong: ~/cvat
oscar@qinglong:~$ git clone https://github.com/cvat-ai/cvat
Cloning into 'cvat'...
remote: Enumerating objects: 86268, done.
remote: Counting objects: 100% (17783/17783), done.
remote: Compressing objects: 100% (1261/1261), done.
remote: Total 86268 (delta 9015), reused 17412 (delta 8770), pack-reused 68485 (from 1)
Receiving objects: 100% (86268/86268), 309.10 MiB | 8.18 MiB/s, done.
Resolving deltas: 100% (58761/58761), done.
oscar@qinglong:~$ cd cvat
oscar@qinglong:~/cvat$ docker compose up -d
```

It will take some time to download all the required Docker images. In the end, the list of the new containers will be displayed in the terminal. You can also see the new container “cvat”, that contains all of them, running in the Docker Desktop application.

The last step is to register a new “superuser” for CVAT. To do so, run the following command in the terminal

```
sudo docker exec -it cvat_server bash -ic 'python3 ~/manage.py createsuperuser'
```

(you will be asked for the Ubuntu password: it is the one that you provided at the end of the “Install WSL” section). Choose a username and a password **that are used in the CVAT application**.

```
oscar@qinglong: ~/cvat
✓Volume "cvat_cvat_cache_db" Created 0.0s
✓Volume "cvat_cvat_db" Created 0.0s
✓Volume "cvat_cvat_inmem_db" Created 0.0s
✓Volume "cvat_cvat_events_db" Created 0.0s
✓Volume "cvat_cvat_data" Created 0.0s
✓Container cvat_redis_ondisk Started 1.9s
✓Container cvat_redis_inmem Started 1.3s
✓Container cvat_opa Started 1.9s
✓Container cvat_clickhouse Started 2.0s
✓Container cvat_grafana Started 2.0s
✓Container cvat_db Started 1.9s
✓Container traefik Started 2.0s
✓Container cvat_worker_import Started 2.9s
✓Container cvat_utils Started 2.3s
✓Container cvat_worker_export Started 3.4s
✓Container cvat_worker_analytics_reports Started 2.4s
✓Container cvat_worker_quality_reports Started 3.2s
✓Container cvat_worker_webhooks Started 3.4s
✓Container cvat_worker_annotation Started 3.2s
✓Container cvat_server Started 3.2s
✓Container cvat_vector Started 2.4s
✓Container cvat_ui Started 3.6s
oscar@qinglong:~/cvat$ sudo docker exec -it cvat_server bash -ic 'python3 ~/manage.py createsuperuser'
[sudo] password for oscar:
Username (Leave blank to use 'django'): oscar
Email address: oscar.papini@isti.cnr.it
Password:
Password (again):
Superuser created successfully.
oscar@qinglong:~/cvat$
```

That's it! CVAT can be used in a web browser by typing "<http://localhost:8080>" in the address bar while the containers are running. (Sometimes the number is not 8080: see below to find the correct one in your configuration.)

Usage

In this section we outline a very basic guide on how to use CVAT. This is not intended to be exhaustive, and we suggest referring to the official documentation (<https://docs.cvat.ai>) for anything not covered in this document. Being a Docker container, CVAT is not found among the programs in the Start menu—you have to launch the

app **Docker Desktop** instead (which by default is not turned on during the PC booting phase), and start the cvat container by selecting it (1) and pressing “Run” (2). After all the sub-containers are up and running, you will be able to access CVAT by typing <http://localhost:8080> in your browser. If port 8080 does not work, it is possible that another application has reserved that port: in that case CVAT chooses another available port. To know which one, open the list of containers under “cvat” by clicking on the small “>” arrow next to it and look for a container named “traefik”: in the column “Port(s)”, there should be two numbers separated by a colon, like “8081:8080”. The *first* of these numbers is the one to write after “localhost:” in the address bar of your browser to access CVAT.

CVAT is designed as a multi-user service, so even if it is installed locally on your machine, it requires you to sign in using the account created during the installation. Insert your email (or username) and password to proceed.

In CVAT you can set up *projects*, which are divided into *tasks*, which in turn can be divided into *jobs*. Let's set up a new project: click either "create a new project" (1) or the tab "Projects" (2), then "create a new one".

In this example, let's call the project "Nephrops". As stated before, we need three labels, "Entrance", "AmbiguousEntrance" and "Burrow", so we create them by clicking on **Add label** : for each type of label, enter its name, choose "Rectangle" in the menu, and choose any colour you like, then click on "Continue". Don't worry if the information disappears, the program saves it nonetheless.

In the end, click on "Submit & Open" to save the project structure and open it.

The next step is to create a task, i.e. a set of resources to be annotated. In particular, the resources of a task can be either one or more images, or one video (it is not possible to assign multiple videos to a single task). Click on the blue **+** button on the right and choose **+ Create a new task** .

Choose a suitable name for the task (for example, the name of the station and/or the timestamp at which the footage has been recorded) and select the resources by clicking in the dedicated area in the window. In this example, we choose to annotate 10 frames. Under “Advanced configuration”, you can select a variety of parameters that can be adjusted to reduce the workload of the resources uploading phase. *(Please note that this software is designed to be hosted on a remote server, with users “uploading” the resources over the internet; in case it is installed locally, “uploading” means “copying the files to the virtual filesystem assigned to the CVAT Docker container”, so nothing is actually transferred outside your machine. However, this means that there will be two copies of the files somewhere in your PC: one in their original location, and one in CVAT’s internal filesystem.)* Useful parameters are:

- **Sorting method:** choose how to sort the list of images in the task. Useful if multiple jobs are defined for the task.
- **Image quality:** if drawing the bounding boxes doesn’t require to be pixel-perfect, you can reduce the quality of the images to save disk space (and bandwidth in case of remote transfer of images). Obviously the information of the annotations will be used with the original images.
- **Start frame, Stop frame and Frame step:** you can select a subset of the frames in a video to be annotated. In particular, as stated in the introduction of this document, you should choose the Frame step to achieve a frame annotation rate of about 2 fps (so, for example, if your video is recorded at 25 fps, choose a Frame step of 12).

In the end, click on “Submit & Open” to save and open the task, or on “Submit & Continue” to save the task and begin creating another one. **Please be aware that the task’s parameters (e.g. image quality, frame steps) cannot be modified later: if you want to add new images/video or change the values of the parameters you have to create a new task (and possibly delete the old one).** After a little wait while the application is copying the files, if you selected “Submit & Open”, the task window will open showing the list of jobs for the task.

Click on the name of the job to open the annotation window.

You can move between different images (or frames of the video) using the controls (1). To create an annotation, click on **Create new rectangle (2)**, choosing the label and the drawing method:

- **By 2 Points:** click on the two points of the image that will be two opposite corners of the rectangle;
- **By 4 Points:** click on four points that will lie on the top, bottom, left and right edges of the rectangle.

Click on "Shape" to start drawing the rectangle.

As a shortcut, you can press the **[N]** key on your keyboard to draw multiple rectangles with the last selected label. Already drawn bounding boxes can be selected by clicking on them while **Cursor (3)** is selected, then resized using the handles, moved by dragging, or deleted by pressing the **[Del]** key of your keyboard. The interface allows you also to rotate them, but **do not do this**: rotated annotations **won't be saved** when exported in the format specified below. Once you are done annotating (or you want to take a break), click on **Save (4)** to save the work.

The last step is to export the annotations for subsequent use. To do so, you can either export all the annotations of a job by pressing the **Menu** button and selecting “Export job dataset” (or pressing the three vertical dots of the job in the “Jobs” tab, then choosing “Export annotations”) or export all the annotation of a task by clicking on the “Actions” button of the task in the “Tasks” tab and selecting “Export task dataset”. In every case, a new window will pop up with the exporting options.

Please choose “YOLOv8 Detection 1.0” as the Export format, do not select “Save images”, and choose a suitable name for the resulting file, then press OK. After a while, a small popup will appear notifying the completion of the export process. To recover the zip archive with the labels, select the “Requests” tab **(1)**, go to the “Export Annotation” row corresponding to the job/task that you just exported, click on the three dots **(2)** and choose “Download”. The zip file will be copied in your Downloads folder.

VoTT

VoTT (Visual Object Tagging Tool; <https://github.com/microsoft/VoTT>) is a free and open-source application developed by Microsoft to visually annotate images and videos. The software is no longer maintained, with the last version released on 3rd June 2020, but can be downloaded and used nonetheless (GitHub release channel to download here: <https://github.com/Microsoft/VoTT/releases>). An example of the output resulting from the annotation of a video frame through VoTT software is reported in Table I.

Table I - Example annotations list returned by VoTT.

<i>image#time</i>	<i>xmin</i>	<i>ymin</i>	<i>xmax</i>	<i>ymax</i>	<i>label</i>
St05_rectangle.mp4#t=1.5.jpg	170	331	215	384	entrance
St05_rectangle.mp4#t=1.5.jpg	84	323	226	409	burrow

Once the program VoTT is installed, you can open it by clicking on its icon. After the initial interface of the application opens, one can choose to start a new project, open an existing local project, or open a remote project. In case a tagging action has already started, you can also see the list of recent projects on the right menu, clicking on one of them will take you to the main editor screen. In the case of first-time tagging, a new project needs to be started.

The procedure is as follows:

- Select “New Project”

- In the next window (Project Settings), choose a name to be displayed (e.g., “AdriaticSea-Day01022024”)
- For “Source Connection” click on “Add Connection” to choose the folder where the videos to be tagged are present

- A new window appears, where you can choose the same “Display Name” as above, while for “Provider” click on “Local File System”; then “Select Folder” and choose the folder where the videos to be tagged are saved, and then click on “Save Connection” (see screenshot below)

- When back to “Project Settings” screen, you have to choose the newly added “Source Connection” through the dropdown menu

- For “Target Connection” choose the folder where the outcomes of the tagging should be saved; it can be the same folder as above, otherwise follow the same procedure as the point above
- For the Frame Extraction Rate, the agreed rate should be set (e.g. “2” fps)
- Click on “Save Project”

The interface with the selected Project will open for tagging, and one of the existing videos in the folder can be selected (once selected it will automatically start; it can be reset with the multimedia controls on the bottom part of the interface)

- Addition of TAGS: click on the “+” button next to TAGS in the top-right corner to add a tag name (e.g. “Entrances”), repeat it for the needed tags (e.g. “AmbiguousEntrance” and “Burrows”)
- Start tagging the frames: select the rectangle icon in the top item list, then drag the bounding box (BB) around the chosen area in the frame for the tag
- Once the BB is drawn, it is coloured with a white frame (meaning it is not tagged), to give a tag to this B you can push the number connected to the selected tag (e.g. 1 for “Entrances”) or click on the chosen tag in the top right list of TAGS.
- In order to facilitate the tagging, you can choose one tag in the list and then click on the “lock” item this way any BB drawn afterwards will be automatically associated with the same tag. To remove the “lock” simply click again on the tag in the list e again on the “lock” item
- To delete a BB you can select it by clicking and then clicking on the “X” next to it
- Once all BBs are tagged in a frame, one can move to the next frame (automatically at the pre-selected fps rate) by clicking on the smaller “right arrow” in the bottom part of the multimedia interface
- You can navigate and update already tagged frames by moving along the timing line or with the navigation arrows with the same multimedia interface below the frame
- In the video timeline on the bottom, the yellow lines are the “visited assets” (i.e., frames that were shown but not yet tagged), while the green lines represent the “tagged assets” (i.e., frames that have tagged items)
- Clicking on this icon on the left menu will present all the chosen project settings, along with statistics about the tagged, visited, etc. frames

Once all frames are tagged (or visited even without tags), clicking on the “Export” icon in the left menu will open the export settings:

- In the “Provider” menu, choose “Comma Separated Values (CSV)”
- In the “Asset State” menu, choose “All Assets”
- Remove the “tick” from the “Include Images” export (there is no need to save the frames)
- Then click on “Save Export Settings”
- Go back to the main screen by clicking on the icon Tag editor
- To export the output files into the previously selected folder click on the export icon in the top menu of the interface. This will export the CSV file named with the chosen name and suffix “-export.csv” (e.g., “AdriaticSea-Day01022024-export.csv”).

This file is the one that should be shared in order to perform the subsequent operations